

Key Informant Interviews

These key informants will be distributed as follows: the fruits, vegetables and nuts industry (3 key informants), tea and coffee (3 key informants), meat and poultry (2 key informants), grains and cereals (3 key informants), dairy (3 key informants), miscellaneous foods industry (3 key informants) while edible oils, marine and sugarcane industry will each have one key informant.

ID 1 Macadamia and Avocado farmer

The conversation revolves around the agricultural sector in Kenya, focusing on the profitability and challenges of macadamia farming. Speaker 2 mentions that macadamia farming does not provide immediate returns, unlike maize, and that it takes 7-10 years to see benefits. Speaker 1 inquires about the support farmers receive, such as irrigation equipment and training on climate-smart practices. The discussion also touches on the potential for macadamia oil and its use in cosmetics and animal feed. Additionally, there is mention of policies aimed at developing the sunflower industry and the impact of airport expansion on cargo transport. The conversation highlights the need for policies that support farmers and the industry, and the importance of market access and job creation.

Macadamia Farming Profitability and Market Challenges

Speaker 2 discusses the profitability of macadamia farming, noting that it does not match other crops like maize.

Speaker 1 questions whether farmers truly benefit from macadamia farming, highlighting the lack of value addition.

Unknown Speaker mentions that macadamia farming does not provide immediate returns, unlike maize.

Speaker 1 and Unknown Speaker discuss the financial benefits of macadamia farming, noting that it takes 7-10 years to see significant returns.

Speaker 1 inquires about the support provided to farmers in terms of market access and the role of middlemen in the process.

Future Plans for Avocado and Macadamia Processing

Speaker 1 asks about future plans for avocado processing, such as oil extraction.

Unknown Speaker mentions that avocado might be used for cosmetics in the future.

Speaker 1 notes that Kakuzu has already ventured into using different crops for cosmetics.

Speaker 2 and Unknown Speaker discuss the importance of getting permission to use land for such purposes.

Speaker 1 mentions having permits for several counties and the need to verify the coverage of these permits.

Policy Development and Job Creation

Speaker 2 talks about the development of policies for the interest of firms and the importance of job creation.

Speaker 1 seeks information on whether policies are effectively addressing their intended goals and contributing to sustainability.

Speaker 2 mentions the initial macadamia policy (China required that farmers from Kenya to import unprocessed macadamia but Kenyan government intervened so that it is imported processed resulting in a back and forth between Kenya exporters of Macadamia and China buyers which resulted in a suspension of the policy for sometime} and its suspension due to market issues.

Unknown Speaker explains the suspension of the policy to mop up excess products in the market.

There is also a policy to plant coffee alongside macadamia to encourage more farmers to get into coffee farming.

Speaker 2 discusses the challenges posed by the global economy and the impact of COVID-19 on the market.

Macadamia Oil and Animal Feed Utilization

Speaker 1 inquires about the availability of macadamia oil in supermarkets and its use in cosmetics.

Speaker 2 confirms that some cottages are using macadamia oil for cosmetics due to its non-edible nature.

Unknown Speaker mentions that the residue from macadamia oil processing can be used as animal feed.

Speaker 1 asks about policies to encourage farmers to diversify from wheat and maize to other crops.

Speaker 2 explains that capacity building is the current focus, with policies developed based on farmer needs.

Policy Implementation and Sector Development

Speaker 2 discusses the collection of levies from policies to reinvest in the sector.

Unknown Speaker mentions the development of policies for nuts and oil crops, including sunflower production.

Speaker 2 highlights the importance of developing policies that benefit both farmers and the industry.

Speaker 1 asks about the designation of directorates and their roles in different counties.

Speaker 2 explains that directorates are designated based on specific needs and the role of the authority in promoting different crops.

Export Potential and Airport Expansion

Speaker 1 mentions the potential for improving export potential in the North Rift region due to the Eldoret international airport.

Speaker 2 discusses the expansion of the airport to handle more cargo and reduce transit costs.

Unknown Speaker notes that the airport expansion aims to benefit both cargo and passengers.

Speaker 1 inquires about the involvement of large farmers in macadamia farming and their market strategies.

Unknown Speaker mentions that large farmers are significant players in the market, using advanced technologies like drones for precision agriculture.

ID2 Avocado Farmer

Problem Stream

Key informant interviewee 2 (ID2) noted that for their avocados, they experience pests and diseases and to counter it, they periodically spray their avocados (mature and seedlings) to avert pests and diseases such as []. Notably, for their greenhouse seedlings, there is a disinfectant footbath for anyone that needs to get into the greenhouse. One of the key challenges that the avocado farmer faces is meeting the conditions for the markets for avocado. ID2 notes that their main markets are in Europe,, China and the Middle East. Notably, for the Chinese market, there instances where they are required to process the avocado (that is ensuring that they are pilled and ripened). This means that they have to incur extra costs in terms of harvesting, processing as well as storage. Considering that they do heavy volumes of avocados { x metric tonnes), they have to incur high energy costs for refrigeration and there are extra labor costs for handling and ensuring that they meet these conditions as opposed to a situation where they are exported unprocessed. The other challenge is that despite such requirements they are unable to get more export earning from the processing of these avocados.

In terms of government policies addressing water shortages, ID2 notes that they have not supported much support from the government in terms of ensuring constant supply of water. They have been using water from a manmade dam which they store water from a drilled well. With this water they are able to irrigate the avocados without any fear for water shortages. ID2 notes that the county water authority recently decided to revise upwards four times the cost of water and sewerage meaning that they would have incurred more operational costs if they did not have their own source of water. Despite a case being in court to challenge the rise in costs of water, they believe that for those operating in the fruits, vegetables and nuts sector, it is plausible to utilize their own sources of water for convenience and to also save on cost.

In terms of the ability of existing energy policies to address rising energy prices, ID2 notes that the cost of energy has been on the rise each year despite the national government mentioning that they intend on lowering the cost of doing

business. As such, ID2 notes that in their farming operations, they utilize solar energy which is available free (taking into account the installation costs). ID2 notes that they use the solar energy to pump water and in operating the farm (lighting, office work and also in the nursery, irrigation). ID2 notes that the cost of energy has reduced by 3/4 that is they went from paying Ksh150,000 monthly electricity costs to Ksh9,000 on a monthly basis.

ID2 notes that fluctuating weather patterns have not had a detrimental effect on their farming operations as they mostly use a greenhouse and utilize irrigation hence they do not depend largely on rainfed agriculture. That is whenever it rains, they are able to store the water as well in the dam for future use. Thus they have enough water all year around. Thus, they have been able to deal with the issue of seasonality of production.

In terms of challenges in adopting new agricultural technologies, ID2 notes that they have to incur high importation costs for precision farming tools, drones and irrigation systems. For drones, there are laws that guide its importation that make it challenging to import it because of perceived security threats they may pose despite its use being intended solely for agriculture. Hence, we have to meet certain stringent conditions coupled with the costs which makes adopting new technology a challenge. ID2 suggests that these tools should attract zero taxes from the government as they will help grow the agricultural sector and in turn earn the government more government revenue.

ID2 mentions that they are usually invited to forums by the county government to share some of the issues. Such forums are also organized by universities for which they partner with in terms of offering students doing Agriculture to intern at the farm. Though they are involved in these forums by the government, ID2 mentions that the government is yet to do more in terms of lowering the cost of doing business and reducing the licenses required to operate.

Policy Stream

ID2 is familiar of The National Food Safety Policy, The National Food and Nutrition Security Policy, Global Food Security Strategy (GFSS) Kenya Country Plan aimed at improving food availability and reducing food waste though they are of the view that these policies are yet to fully meet their intended goals.

In terms of land policies, ID2 notes that they have not been any challenges in terms of policy in the use of land for agricultural use. The challenge only arises when their farm deposits waste and contaminates in areas that will bring harm to the public or when the chemicals they use gets into nearby water bodies. ID2 mentions that they do proper waste disposal and ensure that they contribute to environmental sustainability.

In terms of renewable energy policies, ID2 notes that these equipment need to be zero rated and reduce the regulations to make it easy to transition fully to the use of renewable energy sources. Some of these policies that ID2 is aware of are Green Economy Strategy and Implementation Plan 2016-2030 , National Energy Policy 2018 and the Kenya National Energy Efficiency and Conservation Strategy 2020.

In terms of government policies that help access agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and pesticides, ID2 is not aware of policies that would help access these inputs conveniently. However, ID2 is aware of Kenya Climate Smart Agricultural Strategy: 2017-2026 that is intended to assist farmers in coping with weather fluctuations though ID2 is of the view that the implementation of measures to ensure the policy meets its goal is the challenge hence they have not been able to benefit from the policy. In terms of policies addressing infrastructural needs, there is still more to be done in terms of ensuring that the roads are accessible and there is incentives for storage facilities and support from the government in accessing external markets.

Political Stream

In terms of the political context, ID2 noted that in the period before the general elections in 2022, since the current Kenyan president was not working on reelection, there was not much support (accessing new markets, e.t.c.,) from the political leadership in terms of ensuring that the problems that we face are addressed. In the aftermath of the 2022 election, there was promise by the incoming regime to lower the cost of fertilizer but this campaign promise is yet to be realized and in some instances in 2024, there was an issue of supply of fake fertilizers with not much accountability from the government in ensuring the issues in the distribution and quality control are addressed.

Policy Windows

During the Covid-19 pandemic, an ad hoc committee was formed at the county to come up with strategies to circumvent the challenges that came with the closure of the air space, movement restrictions and in a way we were able to resume the exports of our avocados.

Also, the Gen Z protests that led to the nullification of the Finance Bill 2024 raised our hopes in terms of pushing the government to address our needs such as tax reliefs once dialogue fails.

Milling

ID3 Maize farmer

The conversation revolves around the challenges faced by a large-scale maize farmer in Kenya. The farmer relies solely on rainfall for irrigation due to high initial costs of irrigation systems. They face issues with government-subsidized fertilizers, which are often of poor quality and insufficient in quantity. The farmer suggests involving local farmers in selecting fertilizers to address these issues. They also highlight the high cost of electricity from Kenya Power, which has doubled without any increase in capacity. The farmer mentions the lack of storage facilities and the difficulty in selling produce at profitable prices. Despite these challenges, the farmer values the legacy of their family business and is open to connecting with others in the agri-food industry.

Action Items

- Involve farmers more in selecting appropriate fertilizer types under subsidy programs.
- Explore renewable energy like solar to reduce reliance on expensive grid power.
- Farmers could soon go to the streets like teachers, doctors if maize prices are not set right.

Outline

Water Shortage and Irrigation Challenges

- Speaker 2 inquires about water shortage issues and how they are mitigated.
- Unknown Speaker explains they are rainfed and do not have irrigation, relying solely on rainfall patterns.
- Speaker 1 mentions the impact of climate change on rainfall patterns, leading to unpredictable rainfall and droughts.
- Speaker 1 discusses the challenges of adapting to changing rainfall patterns and the potential for irrigation in the future.

Barriers to Irrigation and Input Access

- Speaker 2 asks about barriers to importing irrigation equipment.
- Unknown Speaker highlights the high initial cost of irrigation investment.
- Speaker 2 inquires about challenges in accessing inputs like fertilizers for large-scale farmers.
- Speaker 1 explains that the government's subsidy program does not fully meet their fertilizer needs, requiring additional resources.

Quality of Fertilizers and Government Subsidy Issues

- Speaker 1 discusses the quality issues with fertilizers provided through the government subsidy program.
- Speaker 1 suggests partnering with companies like Yara for better quality fertilizers.
- Speaker 1 mentions the problem of fake fertilizers and the need for better quality control.
- Speaker 1 proposes involving farmers in the selection of fertilizers to ensure they meet local soil needs.

Policy Gaps and Renewable Energy Use

- Speaker 2 asks about the gap in policy addressing large-scale farmers in subsidization.

- Speaker 1 confirms the policy gap and the need for better alignment with large-scale farmers' needs.
- Speaker 2 inquires about the use of renewable energy in production.
- Speaker 1 mentions limited use of solar energy and reliance on Kenya Power, with high cost increases affecting production.

Government Engagement and Political Promises

- Speaker 2 asks if farmers are invited to forums to air issues and provide solutions.
- Speaker 1 describes being involved in the subsidy program rollout and the subsequent quality issues with fertilizers.
- Speaker 2 inquires about the impact of political promises on production decisions.
- Speaker 1 notes that small-scale farmers struggle to access fertilizers, despite government promises.

Market Challenges and Value Addition

- Speaker 2 asks about challenges in getting produce to the market.
- Speaker 1 mentions value addition efforts to stabilize market prices.
- Speaker 1 discusses the seasonal fluctuations in market prices and the need for storage solutions.
- Speaker 2 inquires about the potential for protests due to policy issues.

Potential for Protests and Legacy of Farming

- Speaker 2 asks if farmers could protest due to policy issues.
- Speaker 1 expresses skepticism about protests but acknowledges the main challenge being input costs.
- Speaker 2 praises the legacy of the farming business and its long-term sustainability.

- Speaker 1 mentions the involvement of Buffalo Millers, a sister company handling milling operations.

Final Remarks and Networking Opportunities

- Speaker 2 thanks Speaker 1 for the insights and expresses pride in their farming legacy.
- Speaker 1 offers to connect Speaker 2 with contacts in the processing industry for further information.
- Speaker 2 appreciates the offer and expresses interest in learning more about the processing side of agriculture.
- The conversation concludes with mutual appreciation and a commitment to future collaboration.

ID4 Dairy Farmer

Problem Stream

In terms of the challenge we face in ensuring the availability and safety of our milk was the cost of energy. Initially, we were paying Ksh250,000 for electricity monthly but once we installed a solar system, the cost of energy dropped to Ksh90,000 monthly. Animal feed was also a challenge but we have utilized silage that ensures that our cattle has access to fodder all year round. We also do trials for the feed that we give to our cattle to a select few of animals to ensure that there are no possible negative effects on the the cows that are being milked.

In terms of water shortages, we have drilled a well and also have a dam which we utilize to irrigate cattle feed (maize, lucerne, napier grass), for the cattle and ensuring that the cattle barn is clean. For the fodder, we use drip irrigation to ensure that the plants always have water. During the dry seasons, the runoff water from the factory and the dairy farm is collected in a dam and used to irrigate the pasture. We also harvest rain water hence we are able to capital on the rainy season and have surplus water. There is no waste at the farm, the runoff water is used for cleaning the cowshed and then directed to the Biogas tanks.

In terms of existing energy policies address rising energy prices and influence operational costs, we are of the view that the government has not done much in terms of ensuring that the energy prices do not escalate to the point that it eats

into our profit margins. We have proposed in forums with the national government but we had to resort to other strategies such as solar energy and biogas since they are readily available and free. For instance, we get the biogas courtesy of the cattle and it has been able to assist in the processing of milk as it has the capacity to power the generators. Our staff also utilize it for cooking which has tremendously saved on cost.

In adopting new technologies, our greatest challenge is the cost of purchasing this equipment. For instance, we recently purchased an automatic milking system (AMS) which will automate the milking of cows. We imported the AMS but did not benefit from the government in terms of tax cuts or incentives inspite our contribution towards social empowerment of our community and contribution to environmental sustainability. Thus the cost of these essential inputs not only the AMS but also precision farming tools and water management tools are subject to taxes despite their ability to contribute to the sustainability of the agricultural sector.

One of the challenges we experienced in getting our produce to the market is the road accessibility. Previously, there was no road connecting the premise of our farm to the main road but we had to hire an excavator to remove the rocks in the road and we gave out our portion of our farm to the public so that there is an accessible road. In this way, we are able to get our produce to the market without a challenge. The other challenge that we used to experience was the storage costs (refrigerator) but with the solar energy and biogas we have been able to keep the milk fresh for longer without incurring high energy costs.

Policy Stream

I am aware of the National Food Safety policy which offers the guidelines for reducing food waste and improving food availability. As a milk farmer, it offers the guideline on milk handling to ensure that the milk is safe for consumption. The policy informed our procurement of the AMS as it will improve handling and processing practices of milk. Also, it has helped with the extension programs with the county government as we get to receive periodical training on best practices in milk production and storage, leading to decreased wastage.

In terms of land policies helping to effectively manage the agricultural land, we have not had any challenge as we can harvest rain water without any challenges.

Considering that the agricultural land was previously hilly, we were able to make adjustments to the land without requiring any permits from the county government. Also, providing part of our land as a road was not a challenge as we did not need any compensation for the government but wanted to empower the surrounding community in terms of an accessible road to the main road.

The renewable energy policies that I am aware of are Green Economy Strategy and Implementation Plan 2016-2030 and Kenya National Energy Efficiency and Conservation Strategy 2020. They have guided our use of biofuel. Previously, we had to cut down 2 trees per day for our heating needs, but with biogas we are able to contribute to environmental sustainability and save 720 trees per year. Also, rather than leaving the methane to escape into the atmosphere, we are converting it into biogas thus helping to reduce the carbon footprint.

Political Stream

Prior to the 2022 general election, farmers within the county were promised that the county would be establishing a milk plant which would buy milk from farmers at better rates to avoid issues of spoilage and poor prices from the well established milking companies. To date, we can only sell our unprocessed milk at Ksh40 a liter which are relatively low compared to other counties where milk is sold at least at Ksh60 a liter. Thus, the political leadership has failed to meet their campaign promises of better prices for milk farmers within the county.

Policy Windows

In 2021 when there was limited rainfall, we had a consultancy forum with the county government where we were encouraged to plant drought-resistant crops particularly the 'Katumani' maize and finger millets which we use to feed our cows. The county was able to provide seeds for farmers that were in attendance and we were able to receive fertilizers under a subsidy program meant to promote the cultivation of these drought-resistant crops.

ID5 Tea farmer

Problem Stream: Challenges in the Agricultural Sector

1. **Dependence on International Market Prices:**

- ID6 explains that international market prices determine tea prices, directly affecting smallholder farmers' earnings.
- Despite the **reserve price of USD 2.43 per kilogram** set to stabilize income, fluctuating global prices continue to impact profitability.

2. **Need for Quality Control:**

- Quality maintenance requires harvesting **two leaves and a bud**.
- ID6 emphasizes that delivering **high-quality tea** to KTDA is essential for securing better international prices.

3. **Limited Land Holdings:**

- Smallholder farmers operate on **small ancestral pieces of land**, making collective KTDA factory processing necessary.
- These land constraints limit production expansion and economies of scale.

4. **Infrastructure and Logistics:**

- ID6 emphasizes the crucial role of efficient transport to the **tea-buying center** and factory.
- Logistical delays can compromise tea quality and freshness during processing.

5. **Payment Dependence:**

- Timely payments are vital for maintaining farming operations.
- ID6 notes that farmers receive payments by the **5th of each month**, enabling management of operational and household expenses.

Policy Stream: Evaluation of Existing Resilience Policies

1. **Support from KTDA:**

- ID6 attributes yield improvements from **250 kg to 600 kg** monthly to **Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA)** support.

- KTDA enhances operations through **smart card technology** and **electronic weighing scales**.

2. Specialty Tea Initiatives:

- Kangaita Tea Factory produces diverse **specialty teas** including black orthodox, green tea, white premium, gold, and silver tips.
- This product diversification supports policies promoting **value addition** and increased farmer earnings.

3. Sustainability Policies:

- KTDA advances **environmental sustainability** through tree planting and using renewable energy from **macadamia shells and briquettes**.
- These initiatives align with Kenya's **Green Economy Strategy and Implementation Plan (2016-2030)**.

4. Technology Integration:

- KTDA implements **SAP business solutions** and **smart card technology** to streamline operations from buying center to auction.
 - These technologies boost efficiency, transparency, and data management.
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Political Stream: Influence of Political Dynamics

1. Dependence on Governance and Market Reforms:

- ID6 recognizes that global economic policies and governance shape market prices and profitability.
- Advancing **value addition** to keep profits within Kenya needs continuous political backing.

2. Collective Ownership:

- The ownership of **54 tea companies** by smallholders under KTDA demonstrates the strength of farmer-led governance.
- Strong political leadership is crucial to protect these structures and ensure equitable value chain participation.

3. Litigation and Advocacy:

- ID6 and fellow farmers actively advocate for industry fairness.
 - Legal challenges against companies like **Unilever** seek to remedy historical inequities and strengthen farmers' supply chain position.
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Policy Windows: Opportunities for Policy Prioritization

1. Value Addition Reforms:

- Former President **Uhuru Kenyatta** pushed for increasing value addition to **90%** of tea production instead of raw tea exports.
- This shift enables farmers to gain more from the supply chain through **local processing and packaging**.

2. Technological Advancements:

- Implementing **smart card technology, electronic weighing scales, and SAP systems** improves efficiency and traceability.
- These innovations support broader technology adoption across the sector.

3. Sustainability Initiatives:

- Focus on **environmental sustainability** and **renewable energy sources** creates opportunities for green farming practices.
- These efforts position Kenya to lead in sustainable tea production.

4. Global Market Dynamics:

- Tea price volatility from events like the **Russia-Ukraine war** highlights the need for farmer protection policies.
- Current market challenges present opportunities to advocate for **stable pricing mechanisms** and **market diversification**.

ID6 Coffee Farmer

Problem Stream: Challenges in the Agricultural Sector

1. Movement Restrictions:

- ID6 explains that coffee parchment transport requires a **movement permit** and is restricted to between **6 AM and 6 PM**, creating logistical complications.

2. Middlemen Exploitation:

- ID6 describes how middlemen compel farmers to sign **unfavorable contracts**, leading to reduced returns and produce exploitation.

3. Pests, Diseases, and Climate Variability:

- The primary coffee varieties (**SL28 and SL34**) are vulnerable to **pests, diseases, and climate fluctuations**, demanding continuous maintenance and investment in pesticides and farming practices.
- These issues are intensified by **climatic changes** in regions like **Mount Kenya**.

4. Real Estate Pressure:

- ID6 highlights how **real estate expansion** into coffee-growing areas threatens farming sustainability and risks the loss of productive land.

5. Input Costs and Profit Margins:

- Though a well-maintained coffee bush produces up to **10 kg of cherries**, expenses for labor, transport, and fertilizers leave farmers with roughly **60%** profit margins.
- Farmers struggle to balance costs with quality maintenance and production targets.

Policy Stream: Evaluation of Existing Resilience Policies

1. Value Addition and Direct Sales:

- ID6 has created value through the "**Stevens Coffee**" brand, processing and selling directly to **local coffee shops, hotels, and restaurants**.
- This direct-to-market approach bypasses middlemen and improves farmer returns.
- Success in **direct sales** depends on securing proper licenses and permits.

2. Support for Processing Infrastructure:

- ID6 relies on **outsourced milling and roasting facilities** due to high equipment costs.
- Farmers would benefit from policies offering **subsidized access to processing equipment** and infrastructure.

3. Agronomic Knowledge and Training:

- ID6 stresses the importance of **education and training** in coffee farming, covering varieties, altitudes, and climate considerations.
- Enhanced **extension services and farmer training** policies could address knowledge gaps.

4. Packaging and Marketing:

- Offering **bulk packaging** options (1 kg, 500 g, and 250 g) for beans and ground coffee has enhanced market access.
- Small-scale farmers need policy support for **branding and marketing initiatives** to compete effectively.

Political Stream: Influence of Political Dynamics

1. Permits and Regulatory Constraints:

- Mandatory **movement permits** for coffee transport create unnecessary bureaucratic barriers.
- Simplified regulations and extended transport hours would reduce farmers' logistical burdens.

2. Market Governance and Fair Pricing:

- ID6's experience shows the need for stronger political support of **fair trade practices** to protect farmers from exploitation.
- **Transparent pricing mechanisms** and direct market access are crucial policy priorities.

3. Land Use Policies:

- Growing **real estate development** pressure demands political action to protect **agricultural land** and preserve coffee-growing regions.
 - Strong land use policies are needed to safeguard productive farmland from urban expansion.
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Policy Windows: Opportunities for Policy Prioritization

1. Value Addition Initiatives:

- ID6's achievements in **value addition** demonstrate the potential for policies supporting **local coffee processing** and branding.
- This strategy strengthens farmers' position in the coffee value chain and reduces raw export dependence.

2. Education and Awareness:

- Current knowledge gaps among farmers call for enhanced **training and education programs**.
- Expanded extension services and workshops would boost farm productivity and coffee quality.

3. Regulatory Reforms:

- **Movement permit** requirements and middlemen issues highlight the need for streamlined logistics and fair market practices.
- Farmers can advocate for **simplified permit processes** and stronger protections against exploitation.

4. Real Estate Development Controls:

- Coffee farm loss to development creates urgency for protective **land use policies**.
- Demonstrating coffee farming's economic and cultural value to policymakers is key to preserving agricultural regions.

ID7 Sugarcane farmer

Challenges in Sugarcane Farming:

1. Delayed Harvesting:

- Harvesting occurs as early as **16-17 months** due to **sugarcane shortages** faced by factories.
- This leads to **lower yields**, such as **50 tons per acre**, compared to optimal harvests.

2. High Transport Costs:

- Transporting sugarcane to factories incurs high costs of about **Ksh 1,400 per ton**, reducing profitability.

3. Input and Operational Costs:

- Cutting costs are approximately **Ksh 500 per ton**.
- The sugarcane seeds are provided by the factory as part of **contract farming arrangements**, which function like a **loan system**.

4. Weed and Pest Control:

- Weed management is handled through mulching using harvested cane residue, reducing the need for frequent weeding.
- Mulching also helps prevent pests, particularly **plant-boring insects**.

5. Profit Margins:

- After deducting transport and operational costs, farmers can earn about **Ksh 200,000 per acre in 20 months**.
- The government-set price for sugarcane is approximately **Ksh 4,900 per ton**.

Policy Stream: Evaluation of Existing Policies

1. Contract Farming Arrangements:

- The factory provides **sugarcane seeds** under contract farming agreements, which ensures a market for the farmers.

- However, these arrangements mean that the factory deducts costs from the final payment, impacting overall profit margins.

2. **Need for Transport Subsidies:**

- High transport costs significantly reduce profitability.
- ID7 suggests that policies supporting **transport subsidies** could alleviate this burden.

3. **Market Pricing Regulation:**

- The **Sugar Directorate** regulates sugarcane prices, but farmers still face challenges with low returns due to high costs of transport and harvesting.
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Political Stream: Influence of Political Dynamics

1. **Role of National and County Governments:**

- The **national government** is responsible for policies related to sugarcane farming, including pricing and subsidies.
- The **county government** benefits from sugarcane farming through revenue shares, though their role in supporting farmers is limited.

2. **Private Sector Involvement:**

- The sugarcane industry in the region is supported by **private sugar companies**, such as **Transmara Sugar Company**.
 - Farmers rely on these private entities for market access and inputs, highlighting the need for political support to balance the interests of farmers and private companies.
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Policy Windows: Opportunities for Policy Prioritization

1. **Addressing Transport Costs:**

- The high cost of transporting sugarcane presents an opportunity to advocate for **transport subsidies** or improved infrastructure to reduce these costs.

2. **Sugarcane Shortages:**

- The current shortage of sugarcane provides a window for policies that encourage more farmers to enter sugarcane farming.
- Investing in **extension services and technical support** can attract new farmers and improve yields.

3. Diversifying Sugarcane Varieties:

- ID7 mentions the potential for new sugarcane varieties that mature faster (in **15 months**). Policies promoting **research and adoption of improved varieties** can enhance productivity and profitability.

4. Support for Private Sector Collaboration:

- Given the reliance on private sugar mills, policies that foster **transparent contract farming practices** and ensure **fair pricing** can benefit farmers.

ID8 Beef farmer

Problem Stream:

1. Underutilization of Potential:

- Despite the large beef industry, Kenya does not produce enough quality beef to meet the demand in cities like **Nairobi and Mombasa**.
- The beef sector is underdeveloped compared to other agricultural sectors.

2. Disease Control:

- **Foot and Mouth Disease** is a major challenge preventing Kenya from exporting beef.
- The lack of comprehensive disease control measures limits the country's ability to access international markets.
- **Vaccination programs** are in place but need improvement and expansion.

3. Lack of Investment:

- The beef sector receives minimal investment, with only **6-7%** of agricultural funding directed to livestock, far below the **15%** recommended in the **Maputo Declaration**.

- The devolved nature of agriculture means counties struggle to prioritize livestock due to limited resources.

4. Regulatory and Structural Issues:

- The beef industry lacks a **dedicated regulatory body** like those for coffee or tea.
- There is poor coordination between **research institutions** and **producers**, meaning valuable research often remains unused.

5. Infrastructure and Production Methods:

- Many cattle in arid and semi-arid areas are of **low-yield indigenous breeds**.
- Obsolete slaughter facilities and lack of modern ranching or feedlot systems hinder productivity and quality.

Policy Stream: Existing Solutions and Policy Gaps

1. Breed Improvement Programs:

- Some counties are initiating **breed upgrading programs** by introducing better-quality breeds to improve carcass weight and meat quality.

2. Disease Control Policies:

- Efforts to establish **disease-free zones** and improve vaccination programs are ongoing.
- Policies supporting **sanitation** and disease management could improve market access and beef quality.

3. Limited Policy Focus:

- The livestock sector suffers from a lack of **dedicated policies and infrastructure** to support beef production, unlike other agricultural sectors.
- Increased government funding and private sector investment are needed to drive growth.

Political Stream: Influence of Political Dynamics

1. Devolution and Resource Allocation:

- Devolution has made counties responsible for animal health and production, but counties often lack sufficient funds.
- National government support is crucial for negotiating with international donors and implementing large-scale projects.

2. Public-Private Partnerships:

- The sector could benefit from increased **private sector involvement** and partnerships to boost investment and modernize production methods.

3. Export Limitations:

- Unlike neighboring countries such as **Somalia** and **Botswana**, Kenya exports minimal beef due to disease control challenges and lack of infrastructure.
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Policy Windows: Opportunities for Policy Change

1. Investment in Infrastructure:

- There is an opportunity to advocate for **increased investment** in slaughterhouses, disease control, and breed improvement to tap into the growing demand for quality beef.

2. Leveraging Donor Support:

- **Multilateral donors** like the **World Bank** and the **African Development Bank** offer opportunities to fund large-scale livestock projects if coordinated by the national government.

3. Improved Research Utilization:

- Bridging the gap between **research institutions** and farmers can provide practical solutions to improve productivity and quality.

4. Disease-Free Zones:

- Implementing **disease-free zones** similar to Botswana could open international markets and improve Kenya's beef export potential.

Problem Stream

The **Problem Stream** identifies the key challenges that affect poultry farming, highlighting areas that require immediate attention.

1. High Feed Costs:

- The cost of poultry feed has escalated, making it difficult to maintain profitability, particularly for layers. This challenge directly impacts production and sustainability.
- **Quote:** "The cost of feeds has gone too high, and the price of eggs is coming down at the moment."

2. Market Competition from Imported Eggs:

- The influx of cheaper imported eggs disrupts local markets, leading to low prices for local farmers and demoralization.
- **Quote:** "When the eggs come from other countries, they affect the price, making us dispose of chickens before they stop laying."

3. Disease Management:

- Poultry farming is susceptible to diseases such as **Newcastle** and **Gumboro**. Managing these diseases requires strict vaccination and hygiene practices.
- **Quote:** "If you don't take care of them, diseases come and create challenges."

4. Initial Capital Costs:

- The rising costs of chicks, feeds, and infrastructure make it difficult for new farmers to enter the industry.
 - **Quote:** "Starting now requires about 200,000 KES for 500 chickens, compared to lower costs a few years ago."
-

Policy Stream

The **Policy Stream** covers existing and potential solutions proposed to address the challenges faced by poultry farmers.

1. Support for Feed Cost Reduction:

- Policies that subsidize feed costs or encourage local production of feed ingredients to reduce dependency on imports.
- **Proposal:** "Farmers need support with feed costs to maintain profitability."

2. Regulating Imports:

- Introducing or enforcing stricter regulations on imported eggs to protect local farmers from market disruptions.
- **Proposal:** "Restricting cheap imports can stabilize local egg prices."

3. Disease Control Programs:

- Enhancing vaccination programs and providing government support for disease management to ensure flock health.
- **Proposal:** "Regular vaccinations and proper hygiene measures are essential to prevent losses due to diseases."

4. Access to Affordable Credit:

- Introducing affordable credit facilities for small-scale poultry farmers to help with initial capital investments.
 - **Proposal:** "Affordable loans can help new farmers manage the high start-up costs."
-

Politics Stream

The **Politics Stream** focuses on the political environment, stakeholder interests, and public opinion that influence poultry farming policies.

1. Farmer Advocacy:

- Poultry farmers advocating for better policies through cooperatives and associations to address high feed costs and unfair competition.

- **Quote:** "Farmers are capable, but when prices drop due to imports, we get demoralized."

2. Government Commitment:

- The need for political will to prioritize the poultry sector through subsidies, market protection, and disease control.
- **Quote:** "The national government needs to support local poultry farmers by regulating imports and lowering feed costs."

3. Devolution Challenges:

- The devolved government structure means poultry farmers rely on county-level policies, which may lack consistency or funding.
 - **Quote:** "Counties should ensure that poultry farming is supported with proper infrastructure and market access."
-

Policy Windows

The **Policy Windows** represent opportunities where problems, solutions, and political will align, making it feasible to implement reforms.

1. Feed Cost Crisis:

- The current crisis of high feed prices presents an opportunity for policymakers to introduce subsidies or incentives for local feed production.
- **Opportunity:** "Policymakers can step in to reduce feed costs, ensuring farmers remain profitable."

2. Market Disruptions:

- The challenge posed by imported eggs creates a window to implement stricter trade regulations and support local producers.
- **Opportunity:** "Addressing the flood of imported eggs can help stabilize the market for local farmers."

3. Rising Demand for Poultry Products:

- Increasing demand for poultry meat and eggs can drive policies promoting local poultry farming and value addition.
- **Opportunity:** "With the right support, farmers can meet the rising demand for quality poultry products."

4. **Post-Crisis Recovery Plans:**

- Economic recovery plans following disruptions (such as pandemics or market collapses) can include targeted support for the poultry sector.
- **Opportunity:** "Incorporating poultry farming support in recovery programs can revitalize the industry."

ID10 Fish farmer

Problem Stream

The **Problem Stream** highlights the key challenges affecting fish farming:

1. **High Cost of Power:**

- Running recirculatory aquaculture systems demands substantial power, significantly impacting profitability.
- **Quote:** "Power costs in Kenya are very high, in fact, punitively high."

2. **High Feed Costs:**

- Fish feed costs remain elevated due to limited local production and market competition.
- **Quote:** "The high feed cost because aquaculture is not a very big industry in Kenya."

3. **Water Scarcity:**

- Water availability poses a critical challenge in semi-arid areas like Machakos.
- **Quote:** "We don't have a lot of resources of water... but with the recycling system, we minimize water use."

4. **Limited Knowledge of Recirculatory Systems:**

- Expertise in operating recirculatory systems is scarce in the region.
- **Quote:** "Recirculation systems are new to this part of our world, and finding people with the knowledge to run them is challenging."

5. **Marketing Challenges:**

- Fish farmers face difficulties in maintaining consistent market access and quality standards.
 - **Quote:** "Marketing is just as important as production...you need to know where you're going to sell."
-

Policy Stream

The **Policy Stream** addresses existing and potential policies to resolve the identified challenges:

1. **Subsidies for Power Costs:**

- Introducing electricity subsidies and supporting renewable energy adoption for fish farmers.
- **Proposal:** "We're trying to mitigate high power costs by going into solar use."

2. **Feed Cost Reduction Initiatives:**

- Supporting local feed production and subsidizing aquaculture feed costs.
- **Proposal:** "If we have more players in aquaculture, the cost of feed will come down."

3. **Water Management Policies:**

- Promoting efficient water management and recirculatory systems in water-scarce regions.
- **Proposal:** "Recirculatory systems help minimize water use and should be supported."

4. **Training and Capacity Building:**

- Establishing government-supported training programs for advanced fish farming techniques.

- **Proposal:** "We are beginning an aquaculture academy to train people on recirculation systems."

5. **Certification Standards:**

- Implementing certification programs to enhance traceability and market access.
 - **Proposal:** "Certification guarantees traceability and helps access supermarkets and international markets."
-

Politics Stream

The **Politics Stream** identifies the political factors influencing aquaculture policies and development:

1. **Government Support for Aquaculture:**

- While initial stimulus programs launched aquaculture initiatives, sustained support remains limited.
- **Quote:** "The idea of Kamudanga Farm came from the government stimulus program... but continuous support is needed."

2. **Collaboration with International Partners:**

- Partnerships with programs like **Fotec Africa** drive innovation and knowledge transfer.
- **Quote:** "We worked hand-in-hand with Fotec Africa to develop Kamudanga Farm."

3. **Devolved Government Challenges:**

- County-level management of aquaculture policies faces resource and expertise constraints.
- **Quote:** "Devolution challenges include inconsistent support and resource allocation for fish farming."

4. **Investment in Renewable Energy:**

- Success requires political commitment to promote and subsidize renewable energy solutions.

- **Quote:** "We are transitioning to solar power to mitigate high energy costs."
-

Policy Windows

The **Policy Windows** represent opportunities where problems, solutions, and political will align for implementing reforms.

1. Transition to Renewable Energy:

- High power costs create momentum for policies supporting solar energy adoption.
- **Opportunity:** "Mitigating high energy costs through solar solutions can be a viable policy direction."

2. Growing Demand for Quality Fish:

- Rising consumer demand for traceable fish products enables certification and quality standard initiatives.
- **Opportunity:** "Certification allows farmers to access premium markets like supermarkets and international trade."

3. Water Efficiency in Aquaculture:

- Water scarcity drives adoption of sustainable recirculatory aquaculture systems.
- **Opportunity:** "Recirculatory systems reduce water use, making them suitable for semi-arid regions."

4. Training Initiatives:

- Skills shortage creates opportunities for public-private partnerships in aquaculture training.
- **Opportunity:** "Establishing an aquaculture academy can bridge the knowledge gap and promote advanced fish farming techniques."

5. Market Development and Infrastructure:

- Market access challenges highlight the need for improved distribution infrastructure.

- **Opportunity:** "Supporting market infrastructure like outlets and distribution networks can help farmers reach consumers efficiently."

Fish farming transcript

1. Overview of Kamudanga Farm

- *"My name is Anton Indetto, and I'm a director of Kamudanga Farm."*
 - *"Kamudanga Farm specializes in aquaculture—specifically fish production—among other activities."*
 - *"We manage the entire value chain, from egg harvesting to hatching to fish production, until our fish reaches the consumer."*
-

2. Adoption of Recirculatory Aquaculture System

- *"We discovered the recirculatory system by chance."*
 - *"With the recycling system, we minimize water usage—only about 10 percent of water needs to be replaced daily."*
 - *"We now produce 100 tons yearly on one acre, whereas traditional methods would require over 20 hectares of ponds."*
-

3. Water and Land Efficiency

- *"We operate in Machakos, a semi-arid area with limited water resources."*
 - *"The recirculation system is ideal for commercial fish farming on small plots—we achieve high production on just one acre."*
-

4. Suitable Fish Species

- *"We rear tilapia and catfish because Machakos's temperatures are perfect for these species."*
 - *"Tilapia and catfish thrive in temperatures between 23 and 30 degrees Celsius."*
-

5. Fish Quality and Taste

- *"Our fish tastes identical to Lake Victoria fish."*
 - *"The water parameters on our farm match those of Lake Victoria."*
 - *"To eliminate any muddy taste in pond fish, we use a purging tank with clean water for 10–12 days."*
-

6. Key Factors for Successful Fish Farming

- *"Success depends on two basic factors: numbers and consistency."*
 - *"Insufficient stocking leads to intermittent market presence."*
 - *"Consistent supply allows us to serve supermarkets, hotels, and restaurants reliably."*
-

7. Certification and Standards

- *"We've earned ARSO (African Organization for Standardization) certification, which is recognized in Europe and Africa."*
 - *"Our certification ensures traceability, quality, and compliance with international standards."*
 - *"We operate completely hormone-free and chemical-free."*
-

8. Hatchery Production Process

- *"In our hatchery, we maintain broodstock with one male to three females."*
 - *"We harvest eggs from females, incubate them in McDonald's jars, and raise them to fingerlings."*
 - *"Our YY technology produces all-male tilapia without synthetic hormones."*
-

9. Nursery and Grow-Out Stages

- *"We transfer fingerlings from the hatchery to nursery tanks, stocking 10,000 per tank."*
- *"During the four-month grow-out stage, fish develop from 50 to 500 grams."*

- *"Each 50,000-liter tank holds 6,000 fish."*
-

10. Purging Process

- *"We keep fish in purging tanks with clean water for 10–12 days without feeding."*
 - *"This process improves taste by allowing the fish to clear their systems."*
-

11. Challenges in Aquaculture

- *"High power costs from machinery operation—we're switching to solar energy."*
 - *"Feed costs are high due to Kenya's limited aquaculture scale."*
 - *"Limited expertise in recirculation systems—we're launching an aquaculture academy."*
-

12. Marketing Strategy

- *"Marketing equals production in importance—we've established our 'Everything Fish' outlets."*
 - *"We distribute to supermarkets, restaurants, and direct consumers."*
 - *"Premium markets require consistent supply."*
-

13. Direct-to-Consumer Outlets

- *"Our 'Everything Fish Restaurant and Sports Bar' locations are in Watamu and along Ngong Road."*
 - *"Customers choose live fish from our aquariums for maximum freshness."*
 - *"Our traceability system ensures product quality and transparency."*
-

14. Future Expansion and Franchising

- *"We're expanding our outlets and franchising the 'Everything Fish' concept."*
- *"Franchising will maintain our certified, high-quality fish standards."*

